

TOURIST SATISFACTION ON HOTEL SERVICES IN DUMAGUETE CITY: AN ASSESSMENT OF SERVICE QUALITY AND BASIS FOR SERVICE IMPROVEMENT STRATEGIES

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ABSTRACT

This study assessed tourist satisfaction with hotel services in Dumaguete City, focusing on service quality as a basis for developing service improvement strategies. Using a descriptive-correlational research design, data were collected from 180 local and international tourists staying in hotels in Dumaguete City through purposive sampling and analyzed using frequency and percentage distribution, weighted mean, and Pearson's correlation coefficient. The findings revealed a very high level of satisfaction with hotel facilities and services and a high level of satisfaction with amenities, with cleanliness and well-maintained facilities receiving the highest ratings and food and beverage services receiving the lowest. Tourists experienced challenges to a moderately high extent, particularly regarding malfunctioning room facilities and inefficient check-in and check-out processes. Significant differences in satisfaction were found based on demographic profile, with satisfaction regarding amenities varying by age ($p = 0.018$) and satisfaction with facilities differing by length of stay ($p = 0.016$). Furthermore, a significant relationship was identified between the challenges encountered and satisfaction levels, indicating that operational issues influence the overall guest experience. The study concludes that although hotels in Dumaguete City generally meet tourist expectations, improvements in facility maintenance, food and beverage services, and operational efficiency are needed to further enhance tourist satisfaction and support the continued development of tourism in the city.

Keywords: *tourist satisfaction, service quality, hotel services, Dumaguete City, facilities, amenities, customer experience, tourism development*

INTRODUCTION

The global hospitality and tourism industry continue to face many challenges in keeping good service quality as tourist expectations, technology, and travel conditions continue to change, especially after the COVID-19 pandemic. Studies show that service quality is one of the most important factors that influence tourists' satisfaction and loyalty all over the world. Recent research also explains that service quality and satisfaction are connected in many ways' different combinations of service factors such as reliability, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy can all lead to tourist satisfaction (Perdomo-Verdecia et al., 2024). In addition, Abdou et al. (2022) found that perceived service quality strongly affects satisfaction and future travel intentions, especially in times when tourists are more concerned about safety and personal experiences. Velastegui-Hernández et al. (2024) also pointed out that satisfaction does not depend only on hotel services but also on other related facilities such as transportation and destination infrastructure. These studies show the importance of continuously studying service quality to help tourism destinations remain competitive and sustainable.

In the Philippines, the tourism and hospitality industry has shown an uneven recovery after the pandemic, with different levels of preparedness among destinations. Otherwise, many hotels have established themselves in the industry, emphasizing their effectiveness and longevity. Marketing strategies have focused on innovative approaches such as local tours, culinary experiences, and wellness activities, driven by personalization to enhance guest satisfaction Chiu et.al. (2024). Similarly, Laspiñas and Tayco (2025) examined lodging establishments in Dumaguete City and found that, although some have adopted basic sustainability and service practices, many still face problems in cost management, service improvement, and staff training. These local findings show that there is a need to measure tourists' actual satisfaction levels and use these results to develop service improvement strategies that fit the Dumaguete tourism context.

However, there are still clear gaps in the existing studies. First, while global studies such as that of Perdomo-Verdecia et al. (2024) show that different combinations of service quality factors can lead to satisfaction, there is limited research on which specific combinations have the strongest effect in Dumaguete hotels. Second, although local studies (Laspiñas & Tayco, 2025)

Lopez, T. (2025) Describe operational challenges, they often do not provide clear, evidence-based service improvement plans that smaller hotels and resorts can apply. Addressing these gaps will not only help improve the local tourism sector but will also add to the wider understanding of how service quality affects tourist satisfaction in developing destinations.

This study aims to assess tourist satisfaction with hotel services in Dumaguete City as a basis for creating service improvement strategies. The city economy depends largely on tourism-related businesses, and the level of tourist satisfaction affects visitor return rates, destination reputation, and local economic growth. By identifying which aspects of service quality most affect tourist satisfaction, this research hopes to provide practical recommendations for hotel managers. The results will also help local policymakers and

tourism planners design better programs for sustainable tourism development in Dumaguete City.

Research Questions

This study aimed to assess the level of tourists' satisfaction with hotel services in Dumaguete City, focusing on service quality as the basis for developing service improvement strategies. With Dumaguete City being a growing tourist destination, understanding how visitors evaluated their experiences was essential for enhancing competitiveness and ensuring sustainable tourism growth. Specifically, the researcher intended to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of tourists' satisfaction on hotel services in terms of the following services quality dimensions:
 - 1.1 facilities;
 - 1.2 services; and
 - 1.3 amenities?
2. To what extent do tourist encounter challenges in the hotel of Dumaguete city in terms of:
 - 2.1 amenities; and
 - 2.2 services?
3. Is there a significant difference in tourists' satisfaction when they are grouped according to their demographic profile in terms of:
 - 3.1 age; and
 - 3.2 number of days spent in the hotel?
4. Is there significant relationship between the challenges encountered by the tourists and the level of satisfaction on hotel services?

METHODOLOGY

Research design. This study employed a descriptive-correlational research design. It is descriptive in nature because it aimed to determine the level of tourist satisfaction with hotels in Dumaguete City in terms of facilities, services, and amenities. It is also correlational because it examined whether there were significant differences in tourist satisfaction when respondents were grouped according to their demographic profile, specifically age, number of hotel stays, and purpose of travel or visit to Dumaguete City.

Research respondents. The respondents of this study were tourists who had stayed in selected hotels in Dumaguete City. Using purposive quota sampling, the researchers selected 180 respondents. This sampling technique was employed to ensure that only tourists with actual experience of staying in and utilizing the services of these accommodations were included in the study. It also ensured that the data gathered accurately reflected the level of tourist satisfaction based on their firsthand experience with the services provided by hotels in Dumaguete City.

To reach the respondents, the researchers personally visited the selected hotels covered in the study and sought assistance from hotel managers and front desk officers

in identifying and approaching qualified guests. In addition, other respondents were conveniently interviewed at Rizal Boulevard while they were visiting or staying in the area. This approach allowed the researchers to gather responses from tourists in both hotel settings and public tourist spaces, ensuring a wider representation of participants.

RESULTS

Table 1.1 presents the demographic profile of respondents categorized by age. The data indicates that the largest proportion of participants falls within the 17–30 age bracket, comprising 64 individuals or 36% of the total respondents. This distribution suggests that a significant portion of respondents are young adults, a group commonly linked to active participation in travel and tourism activities.

Table 1.1
Respondents Profile in terms of Age

Age	Frequency	Percentage (%)
17-30	64	36
31-44	43	24
45-58	51	28
59-72	22	12
Total	180	100

Table 1.2 shows the distribution of respondents based on the number of days spent at the hotel. The data indicate that most participants stayed for 1–2 days, accounting for 74 individuals or 41% of the total sample. This indicates that there is a preference for short-term stays, which are commonly associated with brief visits or weekend travel. Subsequently, the 3–5 days duration accounts for 56 respondents or 32%, indicating a considerable proportion of tourists opting for slightly longer stays, typically for leisure or vacation purposes. The 6– 10 days range comprises 25 participants or 14%, reflecting a moderate level of extended stays. In contrast, longer durations are relatively uncommon: 13 respondents or 7% stayed for 11–20 days, and only 12 respondents or 6% stayed for 21–30 days.

Table 2.1 presents the level of tourist satisfaction with hotel services in terms of facilities. The composite mean of 4.30 indicates a very high level of satisfaction, suggesting that respondents are generally very satisfied with the facilities provided by the hotels. This implies that hotel facilities are effective in providing amenities that meet guests' expectations.

Table 1.2
Respondents' Profile in terms of Number of Days Spent in the Hotel

Number of Days Spent in the Hotel	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1 – 2	74	41
3 – 5	56	32
6 – 10	25	14
11 – 20	13	7
21 – 30	12	6
Total	180	100

Table 2.1
Level of Tourists' Satisfaction on Hotel Services in terms of Facilities

Facilities	$w\bar{x}$	Verbal Description	Verbal Equivalent
1. The establishment has clean and well-maintained buildings.	4.43	Strongly Agree	Very High Extent
2. The room is comfortable and properly ventilated.	4.39	Strongly Agree	Very High Extent
3. The internet connection and communication facilities are reliable.	4.07	Agree	High Extent
4. Safety and security measures are adequate within the premises.	4.39	Strongly Agree	Very High Extent
5. Parking spaces and access areas are convenient for guests.	4.23	Strongly Agree	Very High Extent
Composite	4.30	Strongly Agree	Very High Extent
Legend: Scale	Verbal Description	Verbal Equivalent	
4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High	
3.41 – 4.20	Agree	High	
2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree	Moderate	
1.81 – 2.60	Disagree	Low	
1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree	Very Low	

Table 2.2 presents the level of tourist satisfaction with hotel services in terms of service efficiency and front-office operations. It specifically examines how tourists perceive the quality and organization of service delivery, including the check-in and check-out process, as well as the extent to which overall services meet guest

expectations. The results reveal that tourists experienced a very high level of satisfaction with hotel services, as indicated by a composite mean of 4.30. Respondents strongly agree that the check-in and check-out processes are fast and well-organized, which obtained the highest mean score ($\bar{x} = 4.37$).

Table 2.2
Level of Tourists' Satisfaction on Hotel Services in terms of Services

Services	$w\bar{x}$	Verbal Description	Verbal Equivalent
1. The staff are courteous and accommodating.	4.35	Strongly Agree	Very High Extent
2. The check-in and check-out process is fast and organized	4.37	Strongly Agree	Very High Extent
3. The staff respond promptly to guest requests and concerns.	4.32	Strongly Agree	Very High Extent
4. The overall service provided meets my expectations.	4.23	Strongly Agree	Very High Extent
5. I would recommend this establishment to other tourists.	4.24	Strongly Agree	Very High Extent
Composite	4.30	Strongly Agree	Very High Extent

Legend: Scale	Verbal Description	Verbal Equivalent
4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High
3.41 – 4.20	Agree	High
2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree	Moderate
1.81 – 2.60	Disagree	Low
1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree	Very Low

Table 2.3 presents the level of tourist satisfaction with hotel amenities. It specifically examines guests' perceptions of the additional features and provisions offered by hotels, including overall amenities and food and beverage services, which contribute to the comfort and quality of their stay. The results show that hotel amenities obtained a composite mean of 3.94, indicating a high level of satisfaction among tourists. This suggests that guests are generally satisfied with the various amenities provided during their stay.

Table 3.1 presents the challenges encountered by tourists in relation to hotel amenities in Dumaguete City. It specifically examines the extent to which guests experience difficulties with various hotel amenities, including room facilities, accessibility features, and other provisions that contribute to their comfort and convenience during their stay.

The results show a composite mean of 3.18, indicating that tourists experience these challenges to a moderately high extent. Among the identified issues, the malfunction of room facilities, such as air conditioning and hot water, obtained the highest mean score of 3.61.

Table 2.3
Level of Tourists' Satisfaction on Hotel Services in terms of Amenities

Amenities	$w\bar{x}$	Verbal Description	Verbal Equivalent
1. The establishments offer sufficient recreational or relaxation areas.	3.76	Agree	High Extent
2. The amenities provided are functional and accessible	4.07	Agree	High Extent
3. The food and beverage services meet quality standards.	3.66	Agree	High Extent
4. The amenities are worth the price paid.	4.07	Agree	High Extent
5. I am satisfied with the overall amenities available during my stay.	4.14	Agree	High Extent
Composite	3.94	Agree	High Extent
Legend: Scale	Verbal Description	Verbal Equivalent	
4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High	
3.41 – 4.20	Agree	High	
2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree	Moderate	
1.81 – 2.60	Disagree	Low	
1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree	Very Low	

Table 3.2 presents the challenges encountered by tourists in relation to hotel services in Dumaguete City. It specifically examines the extent to which guests experience service-related difficulties, including check-in and check-out processes, restaurant service, staff responsiveness, and overall operational efficiency. The results show a composite mean of 2.69, indicating that tourists encounter service-related challenges to a moderately high extent. Among the indicators, inefficient or confusing check-in and check-out processes obtained the highest mean score of 2.87.

Table 3.1

Extent of Tourist Encountering Challenges in the hotel of Dumaguete City in terms of Amenities

Amenities	$w\bar{x}$	Verbal Description	Extent of Challenges
1. I find it difficult when the room facilities, such as air conditioning or hot water, are not functioning properly.	3.61	Agree	High Extent
2. I struggle when there is limited or unreliable internet connection during my stay.	3.32	Moderately Agree	Moderately High Extent
3. I feel uncomfortable when the function hall is poorly maintained.	2.97	Moderately Agree	Moderately High Extent
4. I experience inconvenience when there are insufficient or outdated toiletries and bedding provided.	3.11	Moderately Agree	Moderately High Extent
5. I notice a lack of proper signage or accessibility features, making it hard for me to navigate the hotel or resort.	2.92	Moderately Agree	Moderately High Extent
Composite	3.18	Moderately Agree	Moderately High Extent
Legend: Scale	Verbal Description	Extent of Challenges	
4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High Extent	
3.41 – 4.20	Agree	High Extent	
2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree	Moderately High Extent	
1.81 – 2.60	Disagree	Low Extent	
1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree	Very Low Extent	

Table 4.1 presents the significant difference in tourists' satisfaction when grouped according to age in terms of facilities, services, and amenities. In terms of facilities, the computed p-value of 0.262 is greater than the 0.05 level of significance, indicating that there is no significant difference in tourists' satisfaction across age groups. Therefore, the null hypothesis was not rejected. Among the age groups, tourists aged 17–30 obtained the highest mean score (4.41), while those aged 41–60 recorded the lowest mean score (4.19).

Table 3.2
Extent of Tourist Encountering Challenges in the hotel of Dumaguete City in terms of Services

Services	$w\bar{x}$	Verbal Description	Extent of Challenges
1. I feel frustrated when the staff response to requests or complaints is slow or unhelpful.	2.85	Moderately Agree	Moderately High
2. I encounter difficulties when check-in and check-out processes are inefficient or confusing.	2.87	Moderately Agree	Moderately High
3. I am disappointed when the housekeeping service is;			
3.1. Irregular	2.63	Moderately Agree	Moderately High
3.1.2. Inadequate	2.58	Disagree	Low
4. I struggle when rooms service options are limited; and the quality of food is inconsistent.			
4.1.1. Room Service	2.54	Disagree	Low
4.2.2. Restaurant Service	2.50	Disagree	Low
5. I feel neglected when staff are not attentive.	2.79	Moderately Agree	Moderately High
6. I feel neglected when staff fail to provide personalized assistance during my stay.	2.73	Moderately Agree	Moderately High
Composite	2.69	Moderately Agree	Moderately High
Legend: Scale	Verbal Description	Extent of Challenges	
4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High Extent	
3.41 – 4.20	Agree	High Extent	
2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree	Moderately High Extent	
1.81 – 2.60	Disagree	Low Extent	
1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree	Very Low Extent	

Table 4.1
Significant Difference in Tourists' Satisfaction when they are grouped according to their Demographic Profile in terms of Age

Variables	n	Mean	F	p	Decisi on	Remark
Facilities						
(1) 17-30	64	4.41				
(2) 31-44	43	4.30	1.35 8	0.262	Failed to Reject H ₀₁	Not Significant
(3) 45-58	51	4.19				
(4) 59-72	22	4.25				
Services						
(1) 17 – 30	64	4.34				
(2) 31 – 44	43	4.35	0.39 8	0.755	Failed to Reject H ₀₁	Not Significant
(3) 45 – 58	51	4.21				
(4) 59- 72	22	4.30				
Amenities						
(1) 17 – 30	64	4.06				
(2) 31 – 44	43	4.07	3.58 2	0.018	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
(3) 45 – 58	51	3.87				
(4) 59 –	22	3.48				

Table 4.2 presents the significant difference in tourists' satisfaction when grouped according to their demographic profile in terms of the number of days spent in the hotel, specifically in relation to facilities, services, and amenities. In terms of facilities, the computed p-value of 0.016 is lower than the 0.05 level of significance, indicating a significant difference in tourists' satisfaction based on the number of days spent in the hotel

Table 4.2

Significant Difference in Tourists' Satisfaction when they are grouped according to their Demographic Profile in terms of Number of Days Spent

Variables	n	Mean	U	p	Decision	Remark
Facilities						
(1) 1 – 2	74	4.42				
(2) 3 – 5	56	4.32	3.44 1	0.016	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
(3) 6 – 10	25	4.24				
(4) 11 – 20	13	4.15				
(5) 21 – 30	12	3.78				
Services						
(1) 1 – 2	74	4.35				
(2) 3 – 5	56	4.33	0.41 3	0.798	Failed to Reject H ₀₁	Not Significant
(3) 6 – 10	25	4.22				
(4) 11 – 20	13	4.09				
	12	4.25				
Amenities						
(1) 1 – 2	74	3.89				
(2) 3 – 5	56	3.92	1.00 3	0.416	Failed to Reject H ₀₁	Not Significant
(3) 6 – 10	25	4.16				
(4) 11 – 20	13	4.08				
(5) 21 – 30	12	3.73				

Table 5 presents the significant relationship between the common issues encountered by tourists and their level of satisfaction in terms of facilities, services, and amenities. The findings revealed that amenities have a positive and significant relationship with tourist satisfaction across all dimensions. Specifically, amenities significantly correlated with facilities ($r = 0.187$, $p = 0.012$), services ($r = 0.167$, $p = 0.025$), and amenities ($r = 0.382$, $p = 0.001$). Since the p-values are lower than the 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis was rejected, indicating that the challenges encountered in relation to amenities are significantly associated with tourists' level of satisfaction.

Table 5
Significant Relationship between the Common Issues Encountered by the Tourist And the Level of Satisfaction

Variables Correlated	Pearson r	p-value	Decision	Remark
Amenities				
Facilities	0.187	0.012	Reject H _{o2}	Significant
Services	0.167	0.025	Reject H _{o2}	Significant
Amenities	0.382	0.001	Reject H _{o2}	Significant
Services				
Facilities	0.073	0.332	Failed to Reject H _{o2}	Not Significant
Services	0.121	0.106	Failed to Reject H _{o2}	Not Significant
Amenities	0.292	0.001	Reject H _{o2}	Significant

DISCUSSION

Tourist Satisfaction, Service Quality, Hotel Services, Dumaguete City, Facilities, Amenities, Customer Experience, Tourism Development.

Table 1.1 presents the demographic profile of respondents categorized by age. The data indicates that the largest proportion of participants falls within the 17–30 age bracket, comprising 64 individuals or 36% of the total respondents. This distribution suggests that a significant portion of respondents are young adults, a group commonly linked to active participation in travel and tourism activities. Following this group, the 31-44 age range accounts for 51 respondents, representing 28% of the sample. This indicates a substantial representation of middle-aged individuals, who may have greater financial capacity to engage in travel. Conversely, the smallest population is the 59-72 age group, with only 22 participants or 12%.

These observations align with the findings of Leung et al. (2024), who assert that age is a significant determinant of travel behavior, as different age groups demonstrate varying preferences, motivations, and levels of participation in tourism activities.

Similarly, Kang et al. (2022) emphasize that health status plays a critical role in facilitating travel among older adults, suggesting that participation may depend not only on chronological age but also on physical well-being.

Furthermore, the study suggests that age may influence travel decisions, particularly in the choice between domestic and international destinations. Collectively, the findings highlight the role of age in shaping travel patterns, with younger individuals showing higher levels of participation, while older groups may engage less frequently due to considerations related to health and mobility Teixeira, et al. (2022).

Table 1.2 shows the distribution of respondents based on the number of days spent at the hotel. The data indicate that most participants stayed for 1–2 days, accounting for 74 individuals or 41% of the total sample. This indicates that there is a preference for short-term stays, which are commonly associated with brief visits or weekend travel. Subsequently, the 3–5 days duration accounts for 56 respondents or 32%, indicating a considerable proportion of tourists opting for slightly longer stays, typically for leisure or vacation purposes. The 6–10 days range comprises 25 participants or 14%, reflecting a moderate level of extended stays. In contrast, longer durations are relatively uncommon: 13 respondents or 7% stayed for 11–20 days, and only 12 respondents or 6% stayed for 21–30 days. This distribution indicates that long-term accommodation is relatively infrequent among tourists in the area.

These findings are consistent with the study by Kim and Han (2023), who established a negative association between length of stay and customer satisfaction, a relationship observed to be more pronounced in high-end establishments compared to low-end hotels. This implies that guests with longer stays may hold higher expectations, which can influence their overall level of satisfaction.

Furthermore, Oklevik et al. (2021) found that the duration of stay is positively correlated with factors such as age, travel intentions, country of origin, and mode of travel organization, including participation in package tours. Collectively, these results indicate that various demographic and behavioral factors influence tourists' choice of stay duration. The results suggest that while short stays are predominant, understanding the determinants of length of stay is essential for enhancing guest satisfaction and improving the overall tourism experience.

Table 2.1 presents the level of tourist satisfaction with hotel services in terms of facilities. The composite mean of 4.30 indicates a very high level of satisfaction, suggesting that respondents are generally very satisfied with the facilities provided by the hotels. This implies that hotel facilities are effective in providing amenities that meet guests' expectations. The results further show that cleanliness and upkeep of the establishment obtained the highest rating, indicating that hotels place strong emphasis on maintaining clean, well-maintained, and well-presented facilities.

On the other hand, the reliability of internet and communication facilities received the lowest rating, with a verbal interpretation of "high extent." Although still positive, this indicates an area for improvement. The difference in ratings suggests that while the physical environment is highly satisfactory, the digital infrastructure lags slightly behind. Thus, guests are highly satisfied with the traditional aspects of their stay; however,

improving connectivity and internet reliability may further enhance the overall guest experience.

These findings align with the study of Baquero (2023), which showed that customer perceptions of facilities had a positive effect on their overall satisfaction, which was partially mediated by both personnel and business organization. It can be assumed that a good-quality hotel facility can easily achieve high customer satisfaction.

Additionally, the development of accommodation facilities is currently accompanied by a growth in guests' emphasis on quality and structure of additional services. Chanchomsri et al., (2023). Furthermore, Putranto et al., (2023) assert that increasing customer satisfaction in the hotel industry requires maintaining top-notch facilities and outstanding customer service.

Therefore, the findings of the study will show the influence of different service quality dimensions on satisfaction level in hotels. And the overall study proved that four of the service quality dimensions (empathy, responsiveness, assurance, and tangibles) have a positive relation with customer satisfaction, except reliability had a negative relation with customer satisfaction Ali et al., (2021).

Table 2.2 presents the level of tourist satisfaction with hotel services in terms of service efficiency and front-office operations. It specifically examines how tourists perceive the quality and organization of service delivery, including the check-in and check-out process, as well as the extent to which overall services meet guest expectations.

The results reveal that tourists experienced a very high level of satisfaction with hotel services, as indicated by a composite mean of 4.30. Respondents strongly agree that the check-in and check-out processes are fast and well-organized, which obtained the highest mean score ($\bar{x} = 4.37$). This suggests that the hotels demonstrate strong operational efficiency and effective front-office management.

However, although still interpreted as "very high extent," the indicator stating that overall service meets guest expectations received the lowest mean score of 4.23. This slight variation implies that while specific service processes are performed at a high standard, there remains a marginal opportunity to further align the overall service experience with guests' expectations.

The findings indicate a high level of professional competence in service delivery across the hotels surveyed. These findings align with the study of Ali et al. (2021), which emphasized that service quality is a key factor in achieving sustainable competitive advantage in the hospitality industry. They further noted that satisfying and retaining customers is essential for long-term success. This suggests that delivering high-quality service not only enhances customer satisfaction but also fosters customer loyalty.

In addition, Nguyen et al. (2022) highlighted that customer reviews on online platforms after service experiences provide valuable information for potential customers and contribute to a better understanding of customer experience and satisfaction in tourism services. This suggests that guest feedback serves as a direct reflection of their level of satisfaction with the services they receive.

Furthermore, R., P., & N., G. (2024). The study explores various dimensions of service quality, including responsiveness, reliability, assurance, empathy, and tangibles, and evaluates their impact on guest satisfaction. By analyzing data collected from customer surveys and online reviews, the paper identifies key drivers of satisfaction and offers practical recommendations for hotel operators to improve service delivery. The findings suggest that personalized service, cleanliness, and staff professionalism are among the most significant contributors to positive customer experiences.

Overall, the results indicate that hotel services are delivered efficiently and professionally, leading to a very high level of tourist satisfaction and increasing the likelihood of positive recommendations and repeat visits.

Table 2.3 presents the level of tourist satisfaction with hotel amenities. It specifically examines guests' perceptions of the additional features and provisions offered by hotels, including overall amenities and food and beverage services, which contribute to the comfort and quality of their stay. The results show that hotel amenities obtained a composite mean of 3.94, indicating a high level of satisfaction among tourists.

This suggests that guests are generally satisfied with the various amenities provided during their stay. Among the indicators, the overall amenities available received the highest mean score ($\bar{x} = 4.14$), indicating that respondents generally agreed that the hotels provide the necessary features for a comfortable and satisfying stay.

On the other hand, the quality of food and beverage services received the lowest mean score of 3.66. Although this still falls under the verbal interpretation of "high extent," it indicates that the culinary experience is the weakest aspect within the amenities category and may require improvement.

These findings support the study of Lončar and Čerović (2023) emphasized that the overall guest experience is significantly influenced by the quality of the guestroom experience and related amenities. This suggests that amenities play an important role in shaping tourists' overall satisfaction during their hotel stay.

Table 3.1 presents the challenges encountered by tourists in relation to hotel amenities in Dumaguete City. It specifically examines the extent to which guests experience difficulties with various hotel amenities, including room facilities, accessibility features, and other provisions that contribute to their comfort and convenience during their stay.

The results show a composite mean of 3.18, indicating that tourists experience these challenges to a moderately high extent. Among the identified issues, the malfunction of room facilities, such as air conditioning and hot water, obtained the highest mean score of 3.61. This suggests that respondents agree to a high extent that technical failures in essential room features are a major source of inconvenience and frustration during their stay.

On the other hand, the lack of proper signage or accessibility features received the lowest mean score of 2.92, indicating that guests experience this challenge to a moderately high extent. Although this is the lowest-rated challenge in the table, the result still points to the need for improved physical guidance and more inclusive accessibility features for hotel guests.

These findings suggest that while navigation and accessibility concerns are relatively manageable, the reliability of core room utilities remains a more pressing issue that directly affects tourists' comfort and satisfaction in hotels in Dumaguete City. These findings are consistent with the study of Sandi and Mulyadi (2023), who emphasized that proper management of amenities contributes to increased tourism income, as visitors are more likely to choose destinations that provide adequate supporting facilities, safety, and comfort. This implies that inadequate amenities may lead to negative tourist experiences, as reflected in the challenges encountered by guests.

Similarly, Alas and Limos-Galay (2023) highlighted that maintaining consistency in service standards is essential for hotels because it directly influences guest satisfaction and loyalty. This suggests that inconsistencies in facilities and amenities may contribute to negative guest experiences. In support of this, Dambhare and Tiwari (2025) noted that customer satisfaction and loyalty increase when services are aligned with guests' needs and expectations.

Moreover, Pallega (2022) found that although Dapitan City possesses rich natural and cultural attractions, many tourism sites lack adequate basic utilities and on-site facilities despite their accessibility and quality surroundings. This may negatively affect the overall tourist experience, reinforcing the importance of reliable amenities in tourism-related establishments.

The findings indicate that while hotels in Dumaguete City provide generally acceptable amenities, addressing issues related to room facilities, internet connectivity, and basic utilities remains essential in enhancing tourist satisfaction and improving the overall guest experience.

Table 3.2 presents the challenges encountered by tourists in relation to hotel services in Dumaguete City. It specifically examines the extent to which guests experience service-related difficulties, including check-in and check-out processes, restaurant service, staff responsiveness, and overall operational efficiency.

The results show a composite mean of 2.69, indicating that tourists encounter service-related challenges to a moderately high extent. Among the indicators, inefficient or confusing check-in and check-out processes obtained the highest mean score of 2.87. Although respondents only moderately agreed that this is a challenge, it emerged as the most prominent service-related issue. This suggests that administrative delays and unclear procedures may negatively affect guests' initial and final impressions of their hotel stay.

On the other hand, restaurant service received the lowest mean score of 2.50, which falls under the verbal interpretation of low extent. This indicates that respondents generally disagreed that restaurant service is a major source of difficulty during their stay. This finding suggests that while the quality of food and beverage offerings may have been identified as an area of dissatisfaction in previous results, the actual service delivery and efficiency in hotel restaurants are relatively well-managed and do not pose a significant challenge for most tourists.

These findings support the study of Mwacha (2025), who asserted that customer satisfaction, loyalty, and long-term competitiveness in the hospitality sector depend greatly on service quality. Similarly, Gazi et al. (2024) emphasized that accommodation providers must tailor their services to meet guests' specific needs, highlighting the importance of empathetic staff behavior and effective communication. This suggests that poor responsiveness and lack of attentiveness may contribute to negative guest experiences.

In addition, Ali et al. (2021) found that four service quality dimensions like empathy, responsiveness, assurance, and tangibles, have a positive relationship with customer satisfaction, while reliability showed a negative relationship. This indicates that aspects such as staff responsiveness, attentiveness, and empathy play a crucial role in shaping guests' service experiences.

Moreover, Alas and Limos-Galay (2023) emphasized that maintaining consistency in service standards is essential for hotels because it directly influences guest satisfaction and loyalty. This suggests that inconsistencies in service delivery, such as slow response and lack of attentiveness, may negatively affect the overall guest experience.

The findings highlight the need for hotels to strengthen service quality, particularly in terms of staff performance, responsiveness, and operational efficiency, in order to reduce service-related challenges and provide more satisfying tourist experience.

Table 4.1 presents the significant difference in tourists' satisfaction when grouped according to age in terms of facilities, services, and amenities. In terms of facilities, the computed p-value of 0.262 is greater than the 0.05 level of significance, indicating that there is no significant difference in tourists' satisfaction across age groups.

Therefore, the null hypothesis was not rejected. Among the age groups, tourists aged 17–30 obtained the highest mean score (4.41), while those aged 41–60 recorded

the lowest mean score (4.19). Although slight variations in mean scores were observed, these differences were not statistically significant, suggesting that satisfaction with hotel facilities is generally consistent regardless of age. For services, the computed p-value of 0.755 is likewise higher than the 0.05 level of significance, indicating that there is no significant difference in tourists' satisfaction across age groups. Thus, the null hypothesis was also not rejected. Tourists aged 31–40 recorded the highest mean score (4.35), while those aged 41–60 obtained the lowest mean score (4.21). This suggests that tourists, regardless of age, generally perceived hotel services in a similar manner.

Meanwhile, in terms of amenities, the computed p-value of 0.018 is lower than the 0.05 level of significance, indicating a significant difference in tourists' satisfaction according to age. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected. Tourists aged 17–30 and 31–40 obtained relatively high mean scores (4.06 and 4.07, respectively), while those aged 61–80 recorded the lowest mean score (3.48).

This finding implies that older tourists may have different expectations, preferences, or levels of satisfaction regarding hotel amenities compared to younger tourists. These findings are consistent with the study of Pasaco-González et al. (2023), who examined demographic influences on experiential quality and satisfaction and found that age is a significant variable affecting tourists' perceptions of service quality and satisfaction outcomes.

Similarly, Twumasi (2022) reported that different age groups perceive the quality of accommodation and ancillary services differently, indicating that younger and older tourists evaluate hotel facilities and services based on distinct expectations and priorities. Moreover, a study of Ledesma et al. (2022), on guest satisfaction among DOT-accredited accommodation establishments in the Philippines found statistically significant differences in overall satisfaction across age groups, suggesting that age influences how hotel facilities and services are perceived and evaluated.

The study reported a significant effect of age on overall guest satisfaction ($H/U = 8.005$, $p = 0.046$), indicating that younger and older guests assess hotel experiences differently according to their expectations and priorities. These findings suggest that while age does not significantly influence tourists' satisfaction with hotel facilities and services, it has a significant effect on satisfaction with hotel amenities, highlighting the importance of considering age-related preferences in enhancing guest experiences.

Table 4.2 presents the significant difference in tourists' satisfaction when grouped according to their demographic profile in terms of the number of days spent in the hotel, specifically in relation to facilities, services, and amenities. In terms of facilities, the computed p-value of 0.016 is lower than the 0.05 level of significance, indicating a significant difference in tourists' satisfaction based on the number of days spent in the hotel. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected. This suggests that the duration of stay influences how tourists perceive and evaluate hotel facilities. Guests who stay for a longer period may have greater exposure to the physical environment and facilities of the hotel,

allowing them to assess these aspects more critically compared to those with shorter stays.

On the other hand, in terms of services, the computed p-value of 0.798 is greater than the 0.05 level of significance, indicating that there is no significant difference in tourists' satisfaction based on the number of days spent in the hotel. Thus, the null hypothesis was not rejected. This implies that tourists generally perceive hotel services similarly, regardless of the length of their stay. Likewise, in terms of amenities, the computed p-value of 0.416 is also higher than the 0.05 level of significance, indicating no significant difference in tourists' satisfaction across groups based on the number of days spent in the hotel. Therefore, the null hypothesis was not rejected. This suggests that tourists' satisfaction with hotel amenities remains relatively consistent regardless of whether they stay for a shorter or longer period.

These findings indicate that while the duration of stay significantly affects tourists' satisfaction with hotel facilities, it does not significantly influence their evaluation of hotel services and amenities. This implies that hotels may need to continuously improve and maintain their facilities, particularly for guests with longer stays, in order to ensure consistent satisfaction and a more positive guest experience.

These findings are supported by Gemar et al. (2022), who emphasized that tourists' length of stay is a critical variable in tourism planning and destination success, as it influences visitor experiences and decision-making. This suggests that variations in the duration of stay may affect how tourists evaluate different aspects of their hotel experience. Similarly, Bam (2022) highlighted that factors such as visit frequency, nationality, age, education level, and expenditure are significant determinants of tourists' length of stay, implying that differences in stay duration may shape tourists' perceptions and evaluations of hotel services and facilities.

Moreover, Abahre et al. (2023) emphasized the importance of considering demographic factors in shaping visitor satisfaction and tailoring tourism services to meet the diverse needs and preferences of guests. Overall, the results suggest that while tourists' satisfaction with services and amenities remains stable regardless of the length of stay, improvements in hotel facilities are essential, particularly for guests staying longer, to ensure a more satisfying overall hotel experience.

Table 5 presents the significant relationship between the common issues encountered by tourists and their level of satisfaction in terms of facilities, services, and amenities. The findings revealed that amenities have a positive and significant relationship with tourist satisfaction across all dimensions. Specifically, amenities significantly correlated with facilities ($r = 0.187$, $p = 0.012$), services ($r = 0.167$, $p = 0.025$), and amenities ($r = 0.382$, $p = 0.001$). Since the p-values are lower than the 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis was rejected, indicating that the challenges encountered in relation to amenities are significantly associated with tourists' level of satisfaction.

Among the three, the strongest relationship was observed between amenities and satisfaction with amenities ($r = 0.382$), suggesting that issues related to hotel amenities have a greater influence on tourists' overall satisfaction compared to facilities and services. In contrast, service-related issues did not show a significant relationship with satisfaction in terms of facilities ($r = 0.073$, $p = 0.332$) and services ($r = 0.121$, $p = 0.106$), as the p -values are greater than the 0.05 level of significance.

Therefore, the null hypothesis was not rejected for these variables. This indicates that service-related challenges do not significantly affect tourists' satisfaction with hotel facilities and services. However, service-related issues showed a significant relationship with satisfaction in terms of amenities ($r = 0.292$, $p = 0.001$), suggesting that service experiences may influence how tourists perceive and evaluate hotel amenities.

These findings imply that amenities play a crucial role in shaping tourists' overall satisfaction, as issues related to amenities significantly affect satisfaction across all dimensions.

On the other hand, service-related issues appear to have a more limited effect, influencing satisfaction only in relation to amenities. This suggests that tourists place greater importance on the availability, quality, and reliability of hotel amenities in evaluating their overall stay. These findings are consistent with Mareeswaran (2024), who identified a significant positive correlation between various dimensions of service quality and customer satisfaction, emphasizing that amenities and supporting facilities are important determinants of guest experience Mukhlis, et al. (2025)

Furthermore, Hussian et al (2023) emphasized that visitor satisfaction strengthens the relationship between facilities, service quality, and tourists' intention to revisit, suggesting that tourism managers should design effective strategies to enhance service quality and destination attractiveness. Likewise, Lončar and Čerović (2023) found that the overall guest experience is significantly influenced by the guestroom experience, further supporting the importance of amenities in shaping tourists' satisfaction.

The results suggest that addressing issues related to amenities should be a priority for hotel managers, as these significantly influence tourists' satisfaction in terms of facilities, services, and amenities, ultimately contributing to a more positive overall guest experience.

Conclusions

The study found that although tourists in Dumaguete City are generally satisfied with hotel facilities, services, and amenities, several problem areas still exist that may negatively affect their overall experience. While operational services and physical facilities were rated at a "Very High Extent" and amenities at a "High Extent," the results also revealed notable weaknesses that require attention. Despite the generally positive ratings, tourists reported recurring issues, particularly in relation to room utilities such as malfunctioning air conditioning and inconsistent hot water supply, as well as the lower quality of food and beverage services. These concerns indicate that essential comfort-

related and service quality aspects are not yet fully optimized, which may reduce overall guest satisfaction.

The findings also showed that satisfaction is influenced by certain demographic factors. In particular, satisfaction with facilities varies depending on the number of days spent in the hotel, while satisfaction with amenities differs according to age, suggesting inconsistencies in guest experience across different groups.

Furthermore, the study confirmed a significant relationship between the issues encountered by tourists and their level of satisfaction, indicating that operational problems have a direct impact on guest perceptions. This emphasizes that unresolved service and facility issues may negatively affect overall satisfaction and potentially discourage repeat visits. While hotels in Dumaguete City perform well in general service delivery, the presence of persistent operational and facility-related issues highlights the need for targeted improvements to enhance consistency, reliability, and overall tourist experience.

Recommendations

Based on the study's findings, the following recommendations are addressed to specific offices and personnel of Metro Dumaguete College to enhance the school's safety and security system:

Tourists. They may report service and facility-related concerns, such as malfunctioning room utilities and issues with food and beverage services, to hotel management during their stay to help facilitate timely action and service improvement.

Hotel Managers and Owners. Hotel management may prioritize the maintenance and regular inspection of room utilities such as air conditioning and hot water systems and improve the quality and consistency of food and beverage services to address the most common sources of dissatisfaction identified in the study.

Tourism Office. The Tourism Office may strengthen monitoring and evaluation of accommodation establishments, particularly focusing on compliance with service quality standards related to facilities, utilities, and food services, to ensure consistent tourist satisfaction across hotels in Dumaguete City.

Future Researchers. They may conduct further studies focusing on specific hotel operational problems such as utility reliability and food service quality, using a larger sample size and broader geographical coverage to obtain more comprehensive and generalizable findings.

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